

Interview with Artist John Amato

Can you tell me about your first meeting with Norman Raeben?

Yes, I come back to New York and a guy introduces me to Norman. The first time I meet the guy I am still in graduate school. I go to a lecture that he was giving at someone's loft. He said, "You have to hear this guy, he's amazing." So I walk there full of myself, as a young guy of your age. I am highly titled to become a full professor at Columbia. He is giving a lecture on Chekhov and Tolstoj, and this is right down my alley. When he said if there were any questions, I had to throw in my true sense of being the Italian, outspoken, borderline fascist that I was, and I throw this thing out there. I think it was a question about James Joyce to Chekhov. In the context of this absurd intellectual question, he said, in front of everybody, "You're a conceptual idiot. You probably want to become a kind of great writer. Stop reading, stop reading now! You're conceptualizing everything, you're an intellectual, that's all you are, and you will never be a good writer. Now, on the other hand, if you wanna become a good writer, then come to study art with me."

Believe it or not, I was not offended because in my heart I knew he was right. The most profound thing about Norman, besides all of his brilliance, was that he was loving, whatever he dished out. He was intense, he could even crush a fragile person, but this man was absolutely compassionate and loving. It's no surprise that he was the son of Sholem Aleichem. His father was all about love. Norman was bitter, though; he knew things that nobody knows and gave them freely, lovingly, altruistic. Norman brought that to the table. When you see that, you sometimes sit and say, "Let's see when he is going to fail," and it never happened. He was never cruel without being compassionate.

What was the reason for these harsh manners? Was it a part of the methodology?

He knew things that nobody else knows, and he was able to give it freely, and he gave it freely, no strings attached... that's the love. He was altruistic; his essence was this knowledge in recognition of something that had been developed over centuries of development and perception, which had been given to him by tradition. He took from them what they offered him and he made it genuine. And that was Soutine, that was Modigliani, and you can see it in his application. In his understanding of art, he was totally consistent. So whether somebody wants to contest that he had ever lived with Soutine, it doesn't matter. He was so deeply connected to those guys, and experientially, not just conceptually, not like a historian that is all concept. He was definitely experiential in this connection. He brought it with him, and he gave it away freely.

Now, here's a guy who has the gift, and I can tell you, after Norman's death I studied with all kinds of people: from William de Kooning, the Soyers, both Moses and Isaac, all these kinds of supposedly great teachers. They knew nothing, absolutely nothing next to him. He was a giant next to those people. Now, when you have that gift, and nobody can appreciate it for the sake of the knowledge of art, then you get pissed off. At least, until when, in the mid-seventies, he found a group of students that were really interested in art. When he got this group, he was teaching on a level that was just transcendence. He was bigger than life at this point.

Was he still painting at that point?

As a painter, something happened to him. He had psychic issues; there was a time in his history when he became catatonic. He was very sick. He actually pulled himself out of it, but he was fragile after that point, so painting as a real painter, day in and day out, that couldn't be anymore. It put him on his edge. It would have sent him back to some kind of psychiatric circumstance, probably catatonic again. So he did evolve out of it, but it was a health issue—that's why he couldn't paint anymore. But

he would paint on our paintings. He could paint as a teacher. So he would apply paint, and you would see the application, and you'd watch things evolve. The way he taught was exactly the way he painted, so there was this continuity that would blow you away.

Did music have a major role in his lessons?

Yes. One of the things that Norman was clearly connected to is when he's talking about when you hear colors, when you hear a line: the commingling of the senses. When I say commingling, it's when your sensual connection and perception happen. If you see a color relationship, there's a vibration. This is very common in his teaching. It was never about one specific sense, and it was never about the conceptualization of a sense or sense reaction. It was the cognitive connection. The brain is a coordinator of the senses, but only like the way a conductor would be in an orchestra. In the context of the sensual connection to perception, that provides a kind of context for which now the cognition can have some recognition of what's going on and can make sense out of it. So, one of the things that he taught—and he taught this not always literally, but he was always in the metaphor.

What kind of relationship is there between color and space?

We understand color as temperature, and if you really grasp what color does in terms of temperature, hot colors come forward and cold colors go back. So when something like that transpires, it's really happening from a cognitive point of view, and it's not illusionary because you are actually sensing this. When hot colors come forward and cold colors go back, you have space. It's not just linear, like Masaccio, who adopts a linear perspective—that's all—and that's an illusion. It's just a two-dimensional surface with the illusion of three-dimensional space on it. But the great thing about color, and this comes from Norman, is that color became spatial. When you create space of this nature, you create not an illusion of space but the sensuality of space, the actuality of it: it's really happening and it transmits to you. If I show you this color and I put this color next to it, what you actually feel is that this hot color comes forward and this color goes back. Now, if you actually feel that, it is real. That's the sensuality, that's experiential, that is the truth—it's not an illusion. But the other thing about linear perspective—that's an illusion.

Can you elaborate a little more on the concept of metaphor?

Yes. That's poetic rendering. His beautiful gift, because his father was a writer, was the metaphor: always respect and attend to the metaphor, because it combines both the sensuality and the cognition—the two elements that we are. We are linear, with thinking, logical, conceptual, but we are also predominantly sensuous. This is one of his gifts to us; he made this connection. Now, this comes from a long lineage. It isn't something Norman specifically came up with. It goes back to Delacroix, Masaccio, Caravaggio—it goes back to all of them. However, it's an evolutionary development from a perception point of view. We develop over time, and as we develop, we get a greater connection to the conceptual of the surreal, connecting to the senses. This is where we start to become extremely prolific in connecting to the world around us. This is all Norman and was coming out because, you know, he lived with those painters.

I was told he spent several years in Europe, especially in Paris, and that he had the fortune of knowing important impressionist and post-impressionist painters. Is it true?

There's a lot of drama and melodrama about his history, whether it is legitimate or not—the whole thing with Soutine and Modigliani. If you look at the time, it could hardly be possible that he was really that connected with Modigliani. But here's the thing: his father was extremely famous; he was the center of the universe for the whole New York and Parisian Jewish culture. He was also in that

environment because he was a Jewish painter. Within the Jewish culture in art, there's still that sense of persecution and antisemitism, so they have to create their little clique to protect one another in some way, to support one another and to nourish their mutual understanding of life. So it's natural that he would be around Soutine, Modigliani, Matisse... Some of these people were older than him. He was one of the youngsters over there. If you look at the chronology of time, he's gotta be young, like twenty-one, twenty-two years old, but he is still taking it all in. So there's an enormous amount of legitimacy to the fact that he was profoundly influenced by those and by what was genuine in the impressionist and post-impressionist world. He was profoundly affected by it personally. And he was a really, really gifted painter.

At a certain point of his career, he almost put aside his painting activity to undertake a long teaching career. Why?

He had psychic issues, a lot. To know the essence of that is beyond me. In retrospect, having been with him for four and a half years, every day, and knowing him quite intimately, I was a child by comparison. What would I know about behaviorism? What would I know about the psychic issues? In retrospect, having spent a lot of my time after he died being exposed to that, understanding it, I realize that a lot of those things were brought into the teaching process for him. They served a wonderful end.

How did this issue affect his teaching?

He is a guy who's been teaching for forty years, brilliant stuff, and I can tell you, I know all his methodology, which developed over time. By the time I got there, I would say he was at an apex, but it also was an apex of psychosis. I was a young man, bright, capable, but romantic—very romantic. All I wanted to do was to grab the information. Now, that was true of a handful of us. One of the things is that we were hungry for the information like you are now. Bring it all in, just take it all in. You can never have enough of it. You don't care if it's been delivered by a crazy person. Because there's an intuitive connection that you see and it's taking you to levels that you might never reach in any other life. I mean, I was with Lionel Trilling, who was considered more or less a master in terms of comparative literature and creative writing and critical writing. So Norman was trying to pull me away from him, and he succeeded because Norman was giving me the things that I really wanted. I didn't know it consciously. What I do know is, intuitively, something is happening and it's profound and it's taking me to places that I never thought existed. Even Trilling said, "What's going on with you, what are you doing when you're not here?" I was going to be a professor very early in my life if I stayed at Columbia. Then, in 1975, Trilling dies. My mentor dies, and now I say, "What am I going to do now?" I go straight to Norman full time. In 1974, I was being recruited by graduate, brought into this group of a very exceptional place where Trilling accepted only 22 out of six thousand students, and to have me there he raises the number to 23 for his master class.

Can you elaborate a little more on this idea of making things evolve out of space?

Yes. One day he would ask me to pick up an image and paint that image from recall, but not in a linear way; he wanted us to let it evolve out of space. However, when you do it, you still stick to your way of depicting things. Now, in your head, concepts are two-dimensional; in life everything is three-dimensional. So, when you're painting on a canvas, if you're committed to the image and you are letting it evolve out of space, then it should end up three-dimensional on your canvas, not as an illusion of three-dimensional. It should be distorted because space does this, which Picasso showed us. They juxtapose one on another, but when you're painting entirely from your brain, then everything is linear. It is flat. So, everybody that paints entirely an image that they are remembering, they're not seeing it in space. They're seeing it as a concept, an idea, and they could flesh it out. This is a gift

from him. I would probably have never understood Picasso if it wasn't for him. Now, all of a sudden, he comes to your canvas and he paints, and he shows you that the space evolves into the form. He used to paraphrase a lot of painters who knew what he was teaching. All these classic painters, like Picasso, Matisse, Robert Henri. Robert Henri, I think, said, "There's a difference between a painted apple and an apple in paint." Now, an art historian would not understand, "What is he saying?" Well, a painted apple is a concept, so it's gonna be flat. It's gonna look like an apple but it's not really alive. But an apple that arrives in paint by the application of space and lines and graphics, all the elements coming together as a unity, now is alive. This is the kind of thing he would teach you every single day. Think about it for four or five years. I didn't have a clue—so much that it took years to understand. Sometimes it took me ten years, and painting every day, to say, "Oh, now I got it, now I understand what he was talking about."

What kind of people were there in class?

People who needed help in life. All sorts of people, you had everything. As Norman always professed, "Art is for everybody." He was not pretentious; the thing that drove him crazy was the pretentiousness of the art scene out there. All they did was conceptualize for laypersons some rendering of what people were already doing. They didn't care about the cleverness. We already knew all that stuff, but the idea of art is to become personal, to take that information and digest it, not wear it cinematographically. That's what made him angry. People were getting recognized for stuff that was trivial and insignificant in its essence. The people he really cared for were tough, real people.

In an email, you wrote to me, "what Raeben taught, being the son of Shalom Aleichem, was art as a way of life, as is Judaism. So, studying painting with Norman was no less the study of metaphors in the Torah as it was about the development of perception and the growth of 'feeling' as a way of life." Can you elaborate on it?

Now, if you look at Judaism there's a certain commonality. It's a way of life. I was brought up Catholic, and there's a lot of metaphors there, but you know the problem with Catholics is that they wanna see it as literal, and it's not literal. So, art is a metaphor, it's poetic, and out of that poetry, out of those metaphors, comes a higher lesson, a higher recognition of stuff and life. It's not about somebody's right and somebody's wrong. It's "Here's some information, make it your own, try to figure it out." The core of Judaism is based on two things: monotheism and self-responsibility. Monotheism says, by its literal translation, one God. But what is this one? A kind of focus, a wholeness that is connected by commonality. If that's the case, everything is interconnected, and it is all connected by one source. So you have a certain kind of commonality where everybody has a different perspective, but there is no opposition to one another. They're part of a greater all. The other part of Judaism, which is greatly failed, is self-responsibility: responsibility for the self. That elevates things like entitlements, indulgences, things that are entirely about the person being closed or isolated for the sake of their own success to the exclusion of everything around him. You need to be responsible, and if you are, you're not a problem for everybody else. So, when you go into art, as you go into life, if you are responsible for yourself and all your actions, then connectability calls to the table authenticity. You're fighting all the time for what is genuine, what's real. You're constantly learning and growing. And that's the same thing as art. Art is all about finding a kind of connection between actuality and reality. Here's the thing: it's life, it's nature. In order to connect to that you have to love yourself because you have to be involved with yourself in such a way that you're not about anyone else's, but you're about your authenticity. If you do that, then everything's about discovery and recognition and development, and that's what art has always been where it succeeds. It always takes civilization forward: new discoveries, instead of becoming complacent and withdrawn by isolation, grandiosity, and things that are out of context.

Did he teach or talk about the Torah and the Talmud too?

The first time I thought I got the idea of what he was talking about concerning metaphor was one morning. I go into the studio, and he comes in. Here I am, I am this Catholic guy, Jesuit-educated and all that stuff. I got all that baggage, and Norman knows who I am and my history. And he sits there talking to me about the Torah. For the first time in my life, I felt, wait a minute—talking about the Torah and about religion in general, when it is properly understood, is all written by men, and they are all writing about a story. It's a concept, but the problem is, if it was just a concept, how come it is still around? The idea is that there are enough of us around that see it poetically. We say, wait a minute, they are talking around the thing, instead of talking specifically about this thing, and when you talk around the thing you see the greater good come out of it.

Bert Cartwright wrote that Raeben had a sort of rabbinic presence. Is it true?

You know what, there was a little bit of that. You know... if you understand what we just said, rabbinic presence, a rabbinical presence would be something that would be congenial... but, no, he was never that, he was never congenial. He was dogmatic, didactic, extremely didactic, condescending. He was holier than thou, so that's not rabbinical. Rabbinical is like, let me convince you, I am right so let me help you find it. He was more like, this is what I say, and this is the way it is. If you don't like it, get the fuck out of here. That's why some people couldn't handle him. He would beat them up; maybe he was also trying to discourage them from becoming artists.

In an interview released in the mid-seventies, Dylan says that a song should create a “break-up of time.” He also adds that in *Blood on the Tracks* he adopted a technique to do so, which Raeben had taught him.

Dylan understood conceptually a lot of the things that Norman was offering him. He understood that conceptually. Most of those things were all ignitions, they were triggers for him. He didn't understand the depth of this stuff, but it was a moment of enlightenment. It opened up a door, which now he looked inside and said “Oh my God. I have to go there.” Once you go there, unless you maintain continuity with this ongoing relationship with Norman for a while, so that you understand what you're walking into and what it requires from you to grasp that information, you don't get it, but you know it's there now. In Bob's case, he was quick in seeing the doors opening and saying “Wow,” and he needed it. He needed it desperately, as did many other students that came to Norman. They were at a point of their life which was good for them to be introduced to this stuff. Now, what they had to do was not just look at the door but go through it and then start to experience this stuff. Most of them got into the door and went back out. Some of them lingered there, but they would never give themselves the opportunity to do it.

To go to the category of time, specifically... imagine it this way: does time ever stop? No, it's an illusion. We don't know about time being real or not, but we know one thing: that time is constantly moving on. One of the things, if you take a great author like Arthur Miller, *Death of a Salesman*, for instance, which parallels what Norman was talking about. In the play, what is constantly happening is that the thing is moving on, the play is moving forward, the whole time.

I am very intrigued by the idea of a painting being an endless and ever-evolving process that cannot reach a real conclusion. What can you tell me about it?

Norman used to paraphrase Braque when he came to that one. So, it was always understood that, as Braque put it, the painting is never finished ideally and that it's finished by the viewer. The viewer brings his baggage to the painting, and that's the finish of it. However, he often paraphrased George

Braque, who said that “the painting is finished when you have destroyed the idea of its origin.” So, when an artist starts with an idea, it usually is a disaster because now you’re a prisoner to the idea. What he taught is that you cannot be a prisoner. The work has to evolve like time. It develops over time, and it becomes something. That’s the metaphor—you develop that. You can’t walk in knowing it; you have to experience it, travel the journey, and get to this place where all of a sudden it arrives. When you get to the essence you have to shut up, you have to stop. You can’t go on, because if you go on beyond a certain point, you destroy it. Between the abstract and realism, the literal, there is this place we call the semi-abstract world. That’s what he taught—to go to this place where you keep the abstract alive. Then you bring in the cognition, but you only bring it in so much to the point that it’s poetic but not literal.

Do you think Raeben had a strong influence on Dylan?

His whole next album is all of Norman’s words. *Blood on the Tracks* is all Norman stuff. Everything—I mean, “Idiot Wind” (that’s conceptual idiots, saying all kinds of nonsense; they don’t know what they’re saying; it’s an idiot wind), so I mean. “Tangled Up in Blue,” “Shelter from the Storm.” All these things we were talking about in class, metaphorically. Sometimes he stole them, but every good artist steals. I mean half of that album is Norman. Some things are paraphrased, but some are literal—literal rip-offs from him—but that’s OK. “Idiot Wind” is one; I heard him saying any number of times, and the things that he talks about in that context. Remember, “someone has got it in for him”—that’s Norman’s psychosis. But he did get the bigger picture, which is the metaphor, and he made it his own. So what you have is the basic progression of inspiration, of clarity, of things that take us forward. That’s our capacity—to reevaluate something that doesn’t have a proper context, and you take it and make it your own, and you’re making it into something beautiful. We don’t become derivative; we become inspired by.